

QUIZ**LAST NAME: PAPE****FIRST NAME: STEPHANIE****PROGRAM CODE: DIPH****COURSE CODE: ACA-401D****PERIOD NUMBER: 6****INSTRUCTOR: DR. GULMA****Edit or delete text to show actual information below:**

The author applied US conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics.

The author used Turabian (footnotes).

The author did use Zotero to insert references.

The author used the following software: MS Word 2010 on Windows 10.

QUIZ: A SUMMATIVE ASSESSMENT ABOUT ACADEMIC WRITING

1. **Academic essays must fulfill specific criteria to meet recognized scientific standards. Which statement about academic essays is not true? Choose the correct answer.**
 - Generally, an academic essay responds to a question or task.
 - So that the author can convince the reader of his idea, he/she should present the reader his/her thesis developed out of linked aspects by reasoning and evidence.
 - Therefore, essays usually contain a thesis statement, which corresponds to the answer to the research question and an argument.
 - To persuade the reader of one's idea, an author should give some suitable examples, proven by evidence and information from any source identified while researching the topic.¹**

¹ Laurent Cleenewerck and Kabiru Gulma, *ACA-401 Coursepack: Period 1*, 2nd ed. (Bangui, Central African Republic: Euclid University, 2019), 1.

2. **Writing a good essay becomes easier if there is an underlying structure to present the author's ideas and to respond to the research question. Which answer about the recommended essay structure is right?**
- An essay usually comprises four parts: introduction, body, discussion, and conclusion.
 - The essay body consists of paragraphs building up the argument. Thus, each paragraph encompasses a topic sentence, supporting sentences, related evidence, and its analysis, as well as a critical conclusion.²**
 - In contrast to the introduction, the conclusion moves from general to specific.
 - When drafting the essay, one should follow its structure by writing the essay from beginning to end.
3. **Experienced researchers try to adapt their research questions to readers' expectations, which are usually various. Thus, there are conceptual, practical, and applied questions to ask and answer in an academic paper. Choose the correct answer to these three different kinds of questions.**
- The most common questions in academic work are practical. The ones most common in the professions are conceptual. Applied questions are common in academic fields such as business, engineering, and medicine and companies, and government agencies.
 - A question is practical when your answer to So what? doesn't tell readers what to do but helps them understand some issue:
 1. I am working on the topic X
 2. because I want to find out how/why/whether Y (So what if you do?)
 3. so that I can help others understand how/why/whether Z.

² Cleenewerck and Gulma, 3.

- Applied questions provide answers that are not the solution to a practical problem but only a step toward it. In other words, to solve a practical problem, first, we must do research to understand the problem better before we know what to do for its solution.**³
- A question is conceptual when your answer to So what? tells readers what to do to change or fix some trouble-some or at least improvable situation:
1. I am working on the topic X
 2. because I want to find out Y (So what if you do?)
 3. so that I can tell readers what to do to fix/improve Z.
4. **If an author let believe readers other authors' ideas, concepts, or words as his/her own, then he/she is rightly accused of plagiarism. Surely, your instructor has already told you how to avoid plagiarism. Which of the following measures is not sufficient to prevent plagiarism? Choose the correct answer.**
- Acknowledge special or extensive editing in the preface of your published work.**⁴
- Signal every quotation, even when you cite its source.
- Don't paraphrase too closely.
- Usually, cite a source for ideas, not your own.
5. **Nowadays, as a result of standardization needs in academic writing, there are many different established citation styles. The two most common citation forms are notes-bibliography and author-date style.**

³ Kate L. Turabian, *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations: Chicago Style for Students and Researchers*, ed. Wayne C. Booth, Gregory G. Colomb, and Joseph M. Williams, 8th edition (Chicago: University of Chicago Press, 2013), 17.

⁴ Turabian, 52.

Which of the following statements about the two citation styles is wrong?

- In bibliography -style citations, you always signal that you have used a source by placing a superscript number at the end of the sentence in which you refer to it.
- In bibliography -style citations, the citation source is cited in a corresponding numbered note at the bottom of the page or the end of the paper or of each chapter.
- In author-date citations, you always signal that you have used a source by placing a parenthetical citation (including author, date, and relevant page numbers) at the end of the sentence in which you refer to it.⁵**
- In bibliography -style citations, the list of sources at the end of the paper is called bibliography, while in author-date style, it is named the reference list.

6. When writing an academic paper, spelling, style, and grammar also matter. Which of the following answers about punctuation is not true?

- In a vertical list, a period, in the end, is only necessary if the items are complete sentences.
- A colon should introduce a list if the preceding clause is complete and dependent.⁶**
- There is no comma between two independent clauses when the sentence begins with a phrase or dependent clause modifying both.
- If a clause is phrased as a question and part of a sentence, use a question mark after that clause.

⁵ Turabian, 88.

⁶ Turabian, 177.

7. **Academic research entails qualitative and quantitative methods. Both methods rely on observations. Besides some similarities, there are also essential differences between the two approaches. Which of the following statement is not true?**
- Qualitative researchers want to develop theories, while quantitative research aims to test existing theories.
 - Usually, quantitative studies seek confirmation. In contrast, qualitative studies are exploratory.
 - The qualitative research process is cyclic and can be repeated until there is no more information gain regarding developing a theory.
 - Most qualitative researchers select one of the following approaches: (1) phenomenological approach, (2) grounded theory approach, (3) narrative approach, (4) cohort study, and (5) ethnography.⁷**
8. **Qualitative dissertations must present some mandatory contents. Within the framework of well-done introduction and a reasonable conclusion, a sound and detailed description of the methodology applied is vital for readers' understanding of a qualitative study's findings and interpretation. Which of the following items is not a main component of the methodology chapter?**
- Research question and design
 - Literature review⁸**
 - Researchers background, beliefs, biases
 - Population, participants, and sampling technique

⁷ Philip Adu, *Conducting Qualitative Research: Writing the Methodology Chapter* (video), 2016, 12:39, accessed March 26, 2020, <https://eucliduniversity.net/periods/aca-401d-period-4/>.

⁸ Adu, 6:25.

9. When writing on behalf of the World Health Organization (WHO), an author must be familiar with the *WHO style guide*. Which of the following statements about the WHO style guide is wrong?

- As one could conclude from the spelling of the word *Organization* in WHO's official name, American English is the preferred spelling with the WHO headquarters.⁹
- The WHO style guide represents the Organization's house style that is essential for all printed and electronic materials of the WHO headquarters.
- The WHO style guide has replaced the *WHO editorial style manual*.
- In contrast to the former manual, besides editors, all persons dealing with WHO information materials, like staff members and freelance writers, should follow the current style guide.

10. The WHO style guide also provides information beyond preferred spelling, punctuation, terminology, and formatting. Readers also learn details about the structure of the WHO and its member states and how to deal with politically or ethically sensitive issues. Choose the correct answer.

- WHO's highest decision-making body is the World Health Assembly that is usually abbreviated as WHA in all kinds of documents.
- WHO Member States are organizationally grouped into six regions. This grouping is identical to the geographical areas.
- All WHO information must be non-discriminatory to all people around the world. Therefore, the language used within WHO documents should be neutral regarding gender, ethnicity, disabilities, and age.¹⁰

⁹ World Health Organization, *WHO Style Guide* (Geneva: World Health Organization, 2004), 3.

¹⁰ WHO, 55–58.

- The external relations department is responsible that any written politically sensitive material has been cleared by the government concerned before publishing.

BIBLIOGRAPHY

- Adu, Philip. *Conducting Qualitative Research: Writing the Methodology Chapter*, 2016. Directed by The Chicago School. February 3, 2016. Accessed by March 26, 2020. <https://eucliduniversity.net/periods/aca-401d-period-4/>.
- Cleenewerck, Laurent, and Kabiru Gulma. *ACA-401 Coursepack: Period 1*. 2nd ed. Bangui, Central African Republic: Euclid University, 2019.
- Turabian, Kate L. *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations: Chicago Style for Students and Researchers*. Edited by Wayne C. Booth, Gregory G. Colomb, and Joseph M. Williams. 8th edition. Chicago: University of Chicago Press, 2013.
- World Health Organization. *WHO Style Guide*. Geneva: World Health Organization, 2004.

Cleenewerck, Laurent and Kabiru Abubakar Gulma. 2025. ACA-401/ACA 401D Course Pack: Period 1. 6th ed. Washington, D.C.: Euclid University Press. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15245536>.